

Nowhere to Go

Examining the health and well-being of people who have been service restricted from emergency shelters in Hamilton, ON

About This Report

Title

Nowhere to Go: Examining the Health and Well-Being of People Who Have Been Service Restricted from Emergency Shelters in Hamilton, ON

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Publication Date

February 2026

Publisher / Repository

Zenodo (Open-access research repository)

How to cite this report

Bodkin C, DiPelino S. Nowhere to go: Examining the health and well-being of people who have been service restricted from emergency shelters in Hamilton, ON. Zenodo; 2026. doi:0.5281/zenodo.18510483

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Letter to the Community

“Everyone deserves somewhere to call home – this is the message at the heart of our research project”

Dear Hamilton,

In late 2020 we came together as a research team that includes people who have experienced service restrictions, people who have enforced them, people who provide care for those affected and dedicated McMaster students. We were frustrated to see our friends, community members and patients experience health challenges after getting kicked out of shelters. With support from the Hamilton Community Foundation, we wanted to understand how service restriction (banning someone temporarily or permanently from an emergency shelter) impacts a person's health.

It wasn't easy – our first step, a request to access system-wide data from Hamilton's Homeless Individuals and Families Information System (HIFIS), was declined by the City of Hamilton. So, we shifted our approach and focused on the lives and health of 20 people who had been service restricted in Hamilton. These individuals participated in an interview and allowed us to access their local medical records. We analyzed the interview transcripts, summarized the chart review data, examined both qualitative and quantitative results side-by-side to better understand their health and lived experiences.

Any research that examines a social issue runs the risk of blaming individuals for systemic issues and describing the problem without contributing to solutions. To avoid this, we grounded our project in community-based research principles and critical analytical frameworks. Community members were part of designing and leading the research project and we are committed to sharing our results with the community to affect change. Eve Tuck's *Suspending Damage*¹ called us to move beyond merely documenting “peoples' pain and brokenness to hold those in

power accountable for their oppression.” Her work asked us to consider how people who have been service restricted are navigating their own ways to better individual and community health. Jaime Breilh's *Social Determination of Health* helped us understand how structures and systems like racism, criminalization and below-poverty line disability support payments threaten the health of people who are service restricted². It also encouraged us to think about how collective care and organizing by people who use drugs (PWUD) resists and reshapes some of these processes.

Collectively, these insights have carried us far from where we started. Our results point to the need for so much more than a dignified and transparent service restriction process. People who are affected must be empowered to create and implement solutions. This includes providing access to specific and targeted healthcare services for people deprived of housing and PWUD, and realistic alternatives for PWUD so they can safely and reliably access shelters. Uprooting the harms of service restriction means moving upstream. We need to prioritize safe, affordable, supportive housing; meeting basic human needs for food, care, relationship and community; and end the criminalization of PWUD and people deprived of housing.

On a personal level, thank you to the entire team of researchers, many of whom were volunteers and all of whom were unwaveringly committed to the project. Thank you to the Hamilton Community Foundation's Community Health, Education, and Research grant which funded peer investigators, a research coordinator, and our knowledge translation events. Thank you to McMaster University's Department of Family Medicine for the salary support during my research and scholarship fellowship and the department's research team for honouring

our sometimes unusual requests. Thank you to the Shelter Health Network, Hamilton Health Sciences and St Joseph’s Healthcare Hamilton for granting access to medical records. Thank you to HAMSMaRT for allowing me to include research as part of our work to create healthcare that is a liberatory force for patients, practitioners and communities alike. Thank you to the many community members and organizations that attended our results sharing barbecue and workshop events. Above all else, thank you to the research participants who shared their time, stories and lives with us in service to their own communities.

As more of us live increasingly precarious lives under late-stage capitalism and environmental disaster, the brilliance of everyone who contributed to this project and the wisdom shared by research participants reminds me of Arundhati Roy’s words: “Another world is not only possible, she is on her way. Maybe many of us won’t be here to greet her, but on a quiet day, if I listen very carefully, I can hear her breathing.”

May we build another world together, where everyone has somewhere to go.

Claire Bodkin

Principal Investigator, Nowhere to Go

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'C. Bodkin'.

Land Acknowledgment

We conducted our research and wrote this report on Haudenosaunee and Anishinaabe territory. The definition of Indigenous homelessness in Canada³ reminds us that the ongoing violence of colonization and the displacement of Indigenous people from their land, is a root cause of homelessness and health disparities. Ending homelessness in Canada requires Indigenous sovereignty and land back.

Dedication

As a community-based research project, we have relationships with some of the research participants outside of our study. We were heartbroken and angry when one of the research participants died prematurely shortly after their interview as part of the study. We dedicate this report to them, and to everyone who has died too soon because they didn't have safe, accessible, and secure housing.

Executive Summary

We are a team of researchers from the Department of Family Medicine at McMaster University, including individuals with lived experience of homelessness and service restriction, healthcare providers and researchers. This exploratory qualitative study aimed to understand the health impacts of service restrictions from emergency shelters in Hamilton, Ontario.

Emergency shelters are meant to provide temporary housing and connect people to essential services. However, service restriction – the practice of limiting or denying access to shelters – can significantly impact the health of individuals.

We recruited 20 participants through local clinics and community-based organizations. Each participant completed an interview and consented to a review of their medical records from local hospitals and clinics.

Participants described service restrictions as dehumanizing, destabilizing and arbitrary. We generated five key qualitative themes: losing your home should not mean losing your humanity, where am I supposed to go?, the snakes and ladders of service restriction, constantly criminalized and harnessing the wisdom of community. Service restrictions often led to encampment living, where lack of safety and basic necessities worsened health outcomes.

Chart review data revealed high rates of primary care and emergency department use, most commonly for infections, substance-related issues and traumatic injuries. Some emergency department visits led to hospital admissions, mostly for infections and injuries. Patient-initiated discharge was frequent, reflecting discomfort and stigma in healthcare settings.

Participants described a lack of access to timely mental health and substance use care. Abstinence-based policies in shelters pushed people who use drugs to avoid shelters, or to hide their use. Abstinence-based policies also directly led to service restriction. Almost every

participant identified that policing, incarceration and criminalization affected their lives and their health and was directly connected to service restrictions and access to health care. Despite the challenges, participants described a strong sense of community and practiced care for each other.

Participants called for pragmatic, harm-reduction approaches in shelters, including safer use spaces, access to clean supplies and designated shelters for people who use substances. They emphasized the need for transparent service restriction policies with timely appeals and neutral mediation. They also called for being treated with dignity and humanity in healthcare settings, which may address the high rates of patient-initiated discharges.

This study highlights the urgent need for coordinated compassionate responses to the lack of housing and toxic drug supply. Policy implications span all levels of government and include expanding housing access, reforming shelter policies, improving healthcare delivery and reducing criminalization. As a community-based research project, we hope our research will influence the practice of service restrictions and the social context that determines the health of people who are service restricted. We shared our results with service users, community stakeholders, shelter operators and staff, healthcare providers and the City of Hamilton. We published our study in [BMJ Public Health](#). In an area with very minimal research or evaluation, our study lays the groundwork for robust population-level research about the practice and impact of service restriction in Hamilton.

Project Partners

Department of Family Medicine, McMaster University

The Department of Family Medicine is focused on strengthening the impact of family medicine on the health and well-being of all people and their communities. Our team is accomplishing this through collaboration, capacity building and person-centredness. Building on a 50-year history, the department is changing the way health care is designed and delivered in Canada. The department contributed to the project through the time and expertise of its researchers involved in the project, as well as other organizational resources to support project administration and knowledge translation.

Department of Medicine, McMaster University

The mission of the Department of Medicine is to provide outstanding clinical care, to provide superlative education and to maintain their position as a world-leading center for research and innovation. With almost 300 full-time and more than 440 non-geographical full-time faculty, the department consists of 18 divisions spanning the breadth of internal medicine. The department of medicine contributed to the project through the time and expertise of its researchers involved in the project.

Hamilton Social Medicine Response Team (HAMSMaRT)

The Hamilton Social Medicine Response Team (HAMSMaRT) is an organization of healthcare providers and community organizers working to integrate clinical practice, critical analysis and political action. They are an interdisciplinary outreach team providing community-centred care to people for whom conventional health service models present too many barriers to access. They work to advance the idea and practice that health is inherently political and healthcare providers must play a role in bringing about change in the social and material conditions which determine health. HAMSMaRT contributed to participant recruitment and knowledge translation.

Peer Investigators

This project was conceived with input from the outreach coordinator with Keeping Six Hamilton Harm Reduction Action League and HAMSMaRT in 2021. She has lived experience of homelessness and service restriction and supports many people in Hamilton who are currently service restricted. Once we had funding for the project, we hired a peer investigator who also has lived experience of homelessness and service restriction to guide the development of research questions, recruit research participants, conduct research interviews, analyze data and share our results with the community.

Research Team

Claire Bodkin is an Assistant Clinical Professor (Adjunct) with the Department of Family Medicine at McMaster University. She is the Co-Medical Director of HAMSMaRT and has a clinical and research focus on the health of people who experience incarceration and PWUD. She is the lead Principal Investigator for this project, leading the study design and supervising the study.

Kathryn Chan is a recent graduate from the Royal College of Physicians and Surgeons of Canada Emergency Medicine residency program at the Division of Emergency Medicine at McMaster University. She is a co-investigator for this project, and contributed to study design, data collection and analysis.

Fiona Kouyoumdjian is a family physician and Assistant Professor with the Department of Family Medicine at McMaster University, and an Adjunct Scientist at ICES. She has a clinical and research focus on the health of people who experience incarceration, and extensive experience in quantitative health research. She is a co-investigator for this project, and contributed to study design and analysis, as well as methodologic expertise in health research methods.

Larkin Lamarche is a Research Associate and Assistant Professor with the School of Kinesiology and Health Sciences at York University. They bring methodological expertise in qualitative research to the team and on other projects on Robin Lennox's line of research with PWUD. They are a co-investigator for this project and contributed to study design and analysis.

Amanda Lee is a resident physician in the Department of Family Medicine at McMaster University. She is a co-investigator for this project, and contributed to study design, data collection and analysis.

Robin Lennox is a family physician and Assistant Clinical Professor with the Department of Family Medicine at McMaster University. She has clinical focus in addiction medicine and has extensive experience working with PWUD and those deprived of housing in Hamilton. She is a Principal Investigator for this project, and

contributed to study design and analysis, as well as methodologic expertise in community-based research methods.

Olivia Mancini worked in an emergency shelter for a decade in Hamilton. She is a Registered Social Worker at St. Joseph's Healthcare with experience working in Psychiatric Emergency Services and the Schizophrenia Outpatient Clinic. She is a research assistant for this project, and contributed to study design, data collection and analysis.

Rachel Liu is currently a medical student at the Michael G. DeGroot School of Medicine at McMaster University (Hamilton campus). She graduated from McGill University in 2020 with a B.Sc in microbiology and immunology. She is a research assistant for this project and contributed to data collection and analysis.

Marcie McIlveen is currently a SSW student at Mohawk College, and the Director of Programs at HAMSMaRT. She has lived experience of substance use, accessing mental health services, criminal justice, and homelessness. She is a co-investigator for this project, and contributed to study design, data collection and analysis.

Tim O'Shea is an internal medicine and infectious diseases specialist based in Hamilton. He is an Associate Professor with the Department of Medicine at McMaster University, and the

Co-Medical Director of HAMSMaRT. His clinical focus is on infectious diseases in individuals deprived of housing and those who use drugs. He is a Principal Investigator for this project, and contributed to study design and analysis.

Avital Pitkis is a medical student in the Michael G. DeGroot School of Medicine at McMaster University, and previously worked as a registered nurse in an emergency department. She is a research assistant for this project, and contributed to study design, data collection and analysis.

Stephanie Di Pelino is a researcher with the Department of Family Medicine and School of Rehabilitation Sciences at McMaster University. She is the research coordinator for this project. She contributed to study design, data collection and analysis.

Jammy Pierre was born in Ottawa and finished high school in Hamilton. As a peer investigator, she has had to navigate the ins and outs of the shelter system in Hamilton, and brings both lived experience and research expertise to the research team. She knows how to ask questions in a sensitive way that allows research participants to share honestly and openly, and ensures that research findings and recommendations are appropriate and useful to people deprived of housing. She contributed to study design, participant recruitment, data collection, data analysis and knowledge translation.

Suraj Bansal is a Health Sciences student at McMaster University. As a research student with HAMSMaRT, Suraj has worked on various studies on mortality among people deprived of housing in Hamilton, service restrictions, and safer supply programs. He contributed to data analysis and knowledge translation.

We would also like to acknowledge previous team members who contributed to earlier stages of the project, including Denene Furman, Gillian Wiwcharuk, Kaley Connelly, and Anjali Sargeant.

Funding Support

Funding Support was provided by Hamilton Community Foundation (HCF). HCF is a part of a network of Canadian community foundations that provide leadership and financial support that benefit their communities, local needs, and opportunities. Support was provided by HCF community, Education & Research Fund, which supports innovative and applied research in community health.

Our Study

Background

Secure and stable housing is an essential determinant of individual and community health. People who are deprived of housing have a mortality rate up to eight times higher than the general population, with higher rates of cardiovascular disease, respiratory illness, mental health issues and substance use.^{4, 5} This relationship is bi-directional: people with poor health and/or disabilities are more likely to become homeless due to common distal determinants (e.g. colonization, ableism) as well as decreased capacity to participate in the workforce or reliance on below poverty level income support payments; and homelessness itself causes and exacerbates poor health. It is important to recognize that homelessness and mortality are not evenly distributed across the population but shaped by social processes. For example, colonization and anti-Indigenous racism directly contribute to the overrepresentation of Indigenous people among the homeless population in Hamilton at 23% of respondents to the 2021 Point-in-Time Count⁶. Indigenous people are also disproportionately represented among those dying of drug toxicity in Ontario.⁷

Emergency shelters are designed to provide a temporary place to sleep at night and connect individuals with support to access permanent housing. However, in the 2021 Point-in-Time count, only 67% of the 545 people deprived of housing in Hamilton were using an emergency shelter or city-funded hotel room⁸. This suggests that there is a significant prevalence of unsheltered homelessness. The COVID-19 pandemic further strained the shelter system due to isolation requirements, transmission concerns and increased demand. The appropriate release of a large proportion of the prison population early in the pandemic further strained the shelter system. In Hamilton, as elsewhere across Canada, these issues alongside the skyrocketing cost of housing have contributed to an increase in the demand for shelter services beyond their capacity and an increase in the number and size of local encampments.^{9,10}

One barrier to accessing emergency shelters is service restriction: the practice of temporarily or permanently denying access to emergency shelters. Available data suggests that this is a common practice in Canada. For example, almost 1 in 5 women, girls and gender diverse people surveyed for the 2021 Pan-Canadian Women's Housing and Homelessness Survey reporting they had experienced service restriction¹¹, while a 2021 survey of 700 Canadian

workers in the homeless-serving sector found that 44.6% had temporarily banned someone from their service in the last month and 14.1% had permanently banned someone during the same time¹². Despite the frequency and significance of this practice, the reason, duration and process to appeal the service restriction is often unclear to the individual seeking shelter.

Substance use and substance use disorders are common in people deprived of housing, and abstinence-requiring shelter policies present a major barrier to PWUD accessing shelter services. Prior research shows that these policies in shelters can create risk environments for PWUD by forcing people to either avoid shelters and stay outside or hide their drug use and increase their risk of overdose by using quickly and furtively to avoid surveillance and punishment¹³. Shelters in Hamilton often impose restrictions for possession of illicit drugs or harm reduction supplies along with other violations of shelter policies. At the conceptualization stage of the project, we had access to the shelter standards from two of the shelter operators in Hamilton, both of which explicitly state that possession or use of drugs or alcohol or drug use equipment would result in a service restriction. Other reasons (among many) include violence, oppressive language or behaviour, or missing curfew or bed check.

The individual and collective health of people who are service restricted is determined by a wide range of social forces and power dynamics, both internal and external to the service restriction itself. For example, Ontario Disability Support Payments are so low that many people with disabilities, including substance use disorders, are often unable to afford housing. The same people are left to access shelters that have a “no substance use on site” policy. This leads to negative health outcomes – staying outside leads to weather and exposure related illness, or higher risk substance use practices like reusing drug equipment or using alone inside.

Given how common and potentially harmful the practice of service restriction is, a better understanding of its practice and impacts along with potential alternatives is a pressing concern for community health. This study emerged from the collective concerns of patients, peer support workers and healthcare providers affiliated with HAMSMaRT and Keeping Six regarding the health impacts of service restriction that were raised during a routine team meeting. Despite their pervasiveness in shelters, service restrictions are a minimally researched phenomenon with almost no research examining their aftermath. To address this gap, we asked: What are the experiences, patterns of morbidity and healthcare use among individuals who are service restricted?

Research Importance

At the outset of our project, there were no policies or strategies in place to mitigate the use of shelter restrictions, address the needs of those who face shelter restrictions, or systematically report on the use and impact of service restrictions. Each shelter has its own internal service restriction policy, some of which refer explicitly to the City of Hamilton Shelter Standards. Although emergency shelters are subject to standards and funded in part by the City of Hamilton, they operate independently and have a wide range of practices with respect to service restrictions. These discrepancies and lack of oversight, along with widespread abstinence-based service restriction approaches, make it challenging for individuals and communities with already limited resources to navigate the shelter system and access care. There is also minimal research in this area, with no identified studies when we conceptualized our study and one exploratory study on the predictors of service restriction published by Kerman et al after we had completed our data collection.¹⁴

The City of Hamilton has recognized a need to embrace a system-wide approach to service restriction, as evidenced in its November 2020 Request for Proposals for Women’s Emergency Shelter, in which the City of Hamilton references a “willingness to participate in developing a sector-wide service restriction policy.” This Request for Proposals also highlighted the need for a “commitment to harm reduction approaches, including staff training, obtaining harm reduction materials, safe storage of client harm reduction supplies and safe disposal as required.”⁸ During the course of our research project, the City of Hamilton started the process to update its service standards for emergency shelters in Hamilton.

As of August 2025, over 2000 people in Hamilton were currently homeless.¹⁵ Only 312 people were housed through city funding in the last 12 months.¹⁶ From January 1 to October 12, 2025, paramedics responded to 834 suspected opioid overdoses. This

comes alongside the loss of 129 Hamiltonians from opioid related drug toxicity events in 2024, a higher rate than the provincial average.¹⁷ These pressing issues have culminated in the City of Hamilton’s “Declarations of Emergency in the Areas Of Homelessness, Mental Health and Opioid Addiction” approved by council in April 2023, and the Hamilton Opioid Action Strategy endorsed by the Board of Health in June 2023. These declarations of emergency include calls for expanded resources for and access to evidence informed harm reduction interventions including supervised consumption sites and safer supply, opioid agonist therapy, and supportive affordable housing for people with substance use disorders.¹⁸ The opioid action strategy included funding and a call for applicants to operate an 18 month pilot safer use space in a men’s shelter in Hamilton, along with several other relevant actions.¹⁹

Our research responds to the need for a sector-wide service restriction policy, the city’s desire for a harm reduction approach in shelters, and the aforementioned states of emergency. We unpack the scope and impact of service restrictions, with a level of specificity to inform a Hamilton-specific service restriction policy with expanded guidance on harm reduction policies and practices. The involvement of those with lived experience in Hamilton as peer investigators helps to ensure that the recommendations developed by this research project are pragmatic, impactful, and centered in community. Three of the research team members from our project were invited to contribute their feedback on sections of the draft shelter standards as a direct result of our involvement with this research project. Our research results were also shared with people involved in drafting the new shelter standards and other decision makers via our knowledge translation activities.

Research Objectives

Through this project, we aimed to describe the characteristics of people who experience service restriction in Hamilton, and to examine the health impacts of this practice. Our objectives were:

1. To describe the subset of shelter users who are service restricted.
2. To describe health care utilization and morbidity of shelter users who are service

restricted.

3. To better understand the unique experiences of people who are service restricted.

Research Methods

This study used a qualitative interview-based design and reflexive thematic analysis. Initially we had planned to use a parallel convergent mixed methods design, but feedback from peer reviewers on the limitations of our quantitative data led us to restructure our analytic approach to one that was primarily qualitative yet contextualized by quantitative chart review data. Data were collected via semi-structured interviews (see Appendix A for interview guide). Each interview also included the collection of baseline demographic information. The semi-structured interviews asked participants about their mental and physical health, as well as stories about their lived and living experience with homelessness and service restrictions. Interviews were audio recorded and transcribed. Research team members then used reflexive thematic analysis to analyze the transcripts. Reflexive thematic analysis places a central emphasis on the position and subjectivity of researchers as they collect and analyze data and requires researchers to deeply engage with the data and continuously reflect on how their assumptions, world views, and personal knowledge shapes theme generation.²⁰ RL, JP, AL, SD, OM, AP and CB coded the interviews. SB joined the team and we all met regularly to review the codes, create an inductive coding framework, explore and resolve any discrepancies, and generate themes.²¹ Analysis was conducted using Dedoose for coding and categorizing, and Google Jamboard for theme generation and refining. Themes were distributed to the larger research team to consider and give feedback on before two researchers, SD and CB, met to incorporate feedback and finalize the themes.

Throughout the analytic process, we reflected on our position as researchers and how this influenced our understanding and interpretation of the qualitative data. We held a strong social justice and harm reduction orientation evidenced by our community-based organizing and political work (OM, JP, CB) and brought our experiences of being housing deprived and service restricted

(JP), implementing service restrictions (OM), and providing care to people who have been service restricted (CB) to the reflexive thematic analysis. Multiple coders with different lived experiences and positions worked together to analyze the data and generate themes, contributing to the validity of our findings.²² Rigour was further strengthened by the chart review which allowed for triangulation of some of our qualitative findings.

To contextualize the qualitative data, we simultaneously collected quantitative health information by reviewing participant electronic health records from January 1, 2018 and December 31, 2021. We developed and piloted a data collection form (Appendix B) to ensure uniform data extraction across all charts. Quantitative data included demographic data, as well as information about participants' interactions with the healthcare system, including primary care visits and diagnoses, emergency room visits and diagnoses, and hospital admissions and diagnoses. Because of the volume of primary care visits for some participants in our study, only the first 25 visits for each participant underwent full chart review and data extraction to reduce the skew of the data towards the highest users of primary care. Decisions on what diagnoses and reason for visit to extract were made based on what has been documented in the literature regarding morbidity among people deprived of housing and investigator team reflections about what we see among patients we provide care to, and then grouped according to ICD-10-CA codes where available.^{23,24} These were summarized as simple descriptive statistics.

Ethics approval was obtained from the Hamilton Integrated Research Ethics Board, project ID 14035.

Study Participants

We recruited 20 participants for this study. We selected this number to capture a diversity and range of experiences with respect to the experiences and health impact of service restriction, while remaining small enough to analyze the specifics of each interview in depth. Participants were recruited through Shelter Health Network (SHN) clinicians and outreach

workers who were part of the study team, both from clinics and while on street outreach. To be eligible, participants had to have accessed a homeless shelter, experienced service restrictions and accessed health care from a SHN clinic in Hamilton, Ontario.

Community Based Research Principles

We employed several community-based research principles in our study. Our research concerned people in our community, living and experiencing multiple forms of oppression and marginalization, and we wanted our research to contribute to changing community conditions. It is important to note that we are not using the language of community-based participatory research, as we used less robust participatory methods (e.g. we were not engaging with larger groups of people affected by the phenomenon being studied to determine what and how to study service restrictions). Instead, we intentionally formed a research team that included a co-investigator with lived experience of homelessness and service restriction, alongside people with frontline community-based clinical experience providing care to people who have been service restricted. We ensured our team had someone with frontline experience working in shelters and implementing service restrictions, as well as peer investigators to ensure that people with lived experience were involved in directing the research and had the opportunity to develop skills through these roles. Payment was in line with current guidelines from British Columbia Centre for Disease Control (BCCDC) for peer payments.²⁵ We facilitated participation by hosting meetings in person and providing virtual participation options, providing food at all meetings, and supporting the peer investigators with transportation to and from meetings and research events. Finally, we shared our results with a wide range of community members to promote uptake of our research findings.

Critical Analytic Frameworks

We drew on two critical frameworks throughout our project. Eve Tuck’s concept of Suspending Damage²⁶ called us to go beyond merely documenting “peoples’ pain and brokenness to hold those in power accountable for their oppression” to ensure we considered how people who have been service restricted are navigating their own ways to better individual and community health. We came to this framework during our reflexive thematic analysis process. It helped draw out the many strengths participants expressed about themselves and their communities during the interviews and turned our attention towards the possibilities for community-led change.

The Latin American concept of Social Determination of Health helped us understand how structures and systems like racism, criminalization, and below-poverty line disability support payments all intersect to disproportionately undermine the health of people who are service restricted; while collective care and organizing by PWUD to advance harm reduction resists and reshapes some of these processes.²⁷ In contrast to social *determinants* of health, which overemphasizes discrete factors and linear uni-directional causal pathways while obscuring the social forces that create health inequities, social *determination* of health embraces complexity and recognizes that multifaceted intersecting social, political, and ecological forces create the processes and conditions that shape and are in turn shaped by collective and individual health.²⁸ Furthermore, social determination of health recognizes that not all of these processes or conditions are empirically measurable and require us to embrace other modes of inquiry to understand them. Our mixed method analysis allowed us to not just document high rates of illness among people who experience service restriction, but to understand how various social forces within and beyond service restriction serve to attenuate or mitigate them.

Project Timeline

Reflections on the Research Process

The research team used reflection at all stages of the research process, with a keen focus during participant interviews, data analysis, and following our knowledge translation events.

We incorporated the Head, Heart, and Hands framework throughout qualitative interviews. This framework highlights the domains of transformative experience by involving a cognitive domain for critical reflection (head), an affective domain for relational knowing (heart), and a psychomotor domain of deep engagement (hand).²⁹ This framework structured our observations during interviews and grounded our discussion during debriefing sessions. Applying this framework during our debriefing sessions highlighted critical reflections including re-identifying our research purpose while navigating feelings of hopelessness when conducting interviews and drawing on emotions to make connections to further knowledge and ideas to improve our processes. Our debriefs allowed for reflections on what we found helpful while conducting community-based research among a vulnerable population. This included how vital outreach workers were in easing our presence into spaces taken up by participants we were interviewing, providing resources and supplies for interviewees, and discussing how to better compensate and respect those we are interviewing for the benefits of our research.

Our data analysis was guided by a strengths-based approach to generate themes about describing participants, while not ignoring or silencing their stories and truths. When developing themes about the health and experiences of participants, we utilized a social determination of health and solutions-focused approach. We used the concepts of social determination of health, and a critical analysis of the current systems and structures in place to generate themes about participants' health disparities and barriers to healthcare access. Using the concepts of a solutions-focused approach allowed for generation of themes

about participants' suggestions for action or improvement. Our choice in using a solution-focused rather than possibility-focused approach helped in navigating and identifying solutions while recognizing the limitations of our work in "solving" the key research questions.

Reflection continued to be vital during our knowledge translation activities as the team reflected on our purpose of sharing the study results with the community. Presenting our results to those with living and lived experience allowed us to incorporate their feedback and to ensure our perspectives and priorities in the stakeholder workshop aligned with community needs. It also contributed to the rigor of our qualitative work by validating it with community members. When we presented our results to conference audiences that included shelter workers who did not publicly identify as having lived or living experience of service restriction, the response did not always validate study participants' experiences or our findings. In reflecting on these interactions, we believe this may reflect several factors: limited awareness of the differences between how shelter actions and policies are intended and how they are experienced by service users; a desire among shelter workers and operators for research that seeks to understand the perspectives of frontline staff and operators; and our own limitations in fully understanding the shelter sector and constraints. Although similar dynamics were observed during the community stakeholder results sharing workshop, participants there were generally more willing to acknowledge the validity of study participants' experiences and to recognize the work required across healthcare, social services, and municipal government to better support people who are, have been, or are at risk of being service restricted.

Interviews with Research Team Members

Suraj Bansal

Student Researcher

What inspired you to participate in the project?

In my first year of university, I volunteered at local shelters in Hamilton where I learned about the pervasiveness of service restrictions within Hamilton's shelter system and how they can be inconsistently enforced across different shelters. It is already an extraordinarily difficult task for individuals to navigate the shelter system and access healthcare supports. After seeing how these unpredictable sanctions make it even more challenging for so many people, I wanted to understand how this detrimental practice affected the health outcomes and healthcare use in this population.

What was one thing that you learned during this research project? Was there anything that surprised you?

One thing that stood out to me was the shared sense of community that individuals fostered to survive homelessness and service restriction. Their shared experiences within the shelter system and firsthand knowledge of its shortcomings equips them with an invaluable perspective on how to meaningfully improve the situation in Hamilton. This emphasized the importance of empowering people directly affected by service restrictions to partake in the discussion that determines its policy. I felt equally surprised and inspired by the resilience and collective wisdom of this community. It is increasingly apparent that their voices and experiences must play a critical role in reshaping Hamilton's shelter system.

What do you hope will come from this research?

I envision our research laying the groundwork for more robust population-level research on service restrictions. I hope our findings will foster discussions between various stakeholders, including municipal decision makers, shelter operators, frontline staff, and service users. These discussions should focus on developing Hamilton-specific service restriction policies and robust harm reduction practices that prioritize the well-being and dignity of individuals experiencing homelessness. I hope the ensuing discussions establish a more equitable shelter system that not only prioritizes access to housing and healthcare but also offers comprehensive support for mental health and substance use disorders. Ultimately, I hope our research will spark important discussions and evidence-based interventions in Hamilton and other communities grappling with similar challenges.

Olivia Mancini

Co-Investigator

What inspired you to participate in the project?

I participated in the Nowhere To Go Project due to my profound personal and traumatic experience working on the frontlines of the drug poisoning crisis in the men's shelter system over the past decade. I have been involved in situations where service users are given the impossible choice of having to dispose of their sterile harm reduction supplies or giving up their warm shelter bed. Other service users have woken up from an overdose to find out they no longer have a bed to sleep in for the night because they were service restricted for overdosing in the shelter, despite this being a medical emergency.

One service user was removed from his private room and service restricted for drinking with another service user. He expressed a deep amount of shame to me, and that night he died of an overdose. The guilt consumed me as I was the one who had to implement the service restriction, a deep moral injury that I still battle with today. I was complicit in causing significant harm to service users due to inadequate drug policy and practice that is life threatening to people who use drugs. Today, I advocate for best practices of harm reduction in emergency shelters, and I am deeply inspired by this research as it is an opportunity for shelter providers to be agents of change and pioneer innovative solutions to meet the needs of people who use drugs.

What was one thing that you learned during this research project? Was there anything that surprised you?

What I learned during the research project is the importance of meaningful engagement and involvement of people With lived and living experience. The work of the Peer Investigator on our team helped us to build rapport with research study participants and shaped our interpretation of the qualitative data and theme generation. For example, the Peer Investigator highlighted the codes and themes related to needing a transparent and accountable service restriction process.

Additionally, mixed methods research provided a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the research topic as we were able to capture a rich and deep data set, increasing the validity of our research. Mixed methods allowed us to see that someone's health status (e.g. number and type of diagnoses) are underpinned by complex pathways (trauma, constant threats to psychological and physical safety) and that they face numerous barriers to achieving/maintaining good health as a result of service restrictions (e.g. not being able to access familiar health and social services, losing all of their belongings, having to hide their drug use).

What was most surprising during the research project, was during the qualitative interviews, there were no questions asked about police. However, there was a common theme of constant police presence when accessing healthcare and how it carries a threat of arrest that negatively affects healthcare experiences and deters people from seeking care.

What do you hope will come from this research?

I hope this research will inspire shelter providers to implement evidence-based harm reduction measures with consistency across all shelter systems that are developed and led by drug user groups. In particular, the provision of harm reduction supplies without surveillance, ending service restrictions related to drug use, installing sharps containers in washrooms and individual stalls, hiring peers to facilitate educational workshops on overdose prevention and response, and safer use spaces enacted in all emergency shelters to fully maximize the health and safety of people who use drugs.

Jammy Pierre

Peer Investigator

What inspired you to participate in the project?

As a person with lived experience of homelessness, I felt inspired to participate in this project to help give back to my community. I have had to navigate the ins and outs of the shelter system in Hamilton and felt like I could bring a level of knowledge and expertise to the research team. Given my personal connection to this work as well as to the participants involved, I recognized the importance of my contributions in supporting appropriate recommendations that the project intends to put forward.

What was one thing that you learned during this research project? Was there anything that surprised you?

Many of those I interviewed were friends or fellow members of the shelter community. Despite this, I was surprised by how vulnerable my peers became when interviewed, a side of them I had not seen before. Given this was my first experience as a member of a research team, I was unaware of the thoroughness and time that is required to conduct both qualitative and quantitative research.

However, I am most grateful that this experience as a peer investigator allowed me to develop my qualitative interviewing skills. Through this project, I was equipped with interviewing techniques that

allowed me to learn about the fundamentals of qualitative research, as well as how to navigate difficult conversations while conducting interviews. This experience has inspired me to pursue further opportunities as a qualitative interviewer, making me feel a newfound sense of pride and accomplishment.

What do you hope will come from this research?

I hope this research can shed light on the need for transparency and a transformation in the procedures regarding shelter restrictions. This community has been unnecessarily restricted and exposed to harmful standards. There is a need to end the use of unnecessary restrictions and recognize the danger that this causes among the shelter community.

I am also hopeful that this work highlights and further opens the discussion of safe use supply and safe use spaces. I am passionate about helping be a voice for providing people who use drugs with a fighting chance to survive. There is a need for safe use supply and safe use spaces to become a larger part of the discussion surrounding emergency shelters to support people who use drugs.

Study Results

Cohort characteristics

Participants ranged in age from 26 to 69 years old, with an average age of 42.9 years. Almost one-third (30%) of participants self-identified as Indigenous while 5% identified as Black and 55% as White. The majority (75%) of participants self-identified as men. We recruited using convenience sampling and recognize that people who have been service restricted may have unique characteristics than the broader population of people deprived of housing. To better understand these differences, we compared our study sample to the 2021 Point in Time Connection (PiTC) results¹. While the study sample was similar in age and representation of Indigenous people, it included a lower percentage of Black people and women compared to the PiTC respondents. This comparison highlights potential gaps in our study population and points to areas for further exploration around the unique demographics of people who are service restricted.³⁰

Table 1 Participant Characteristics

Participant Characteristics (N = 20)		
Age	Years	
Mean	42.9	
Minimum	26	
Maximum	69	
Gender*	N	%
Man	15	75
Woman	4	20
Transgender Woman	1	5
Sexual Orientation*	N	%
Straight	17	85
Asexual	1	5
Lesbian	1	5
Bisexual	1	5
Racial Identity*.*	N	%
Métis	2	10
First Nations	4	20
White	11	55
Black	1	5
Mixed Race	3	3

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¹ 51% of respondents were between the ages of 31 and 49 years old, 23% self-identified as Indigenous, 10% self-identified as Black-African, Black-Canadian/American, or Black-Afro-Caribbean / Afro-Latinx, and 47% self-identified as men.

Income+	N	%
Ontario Disability Support Program	12	60
Pension Income	1	5
Ontario Works	4	20
Informal Economies**	13	65
No Income	1	5

*Self-identified

+ Does not add to 100% as some participants identified with more than one category

**Panhandling, odd jobs, casual jobs, casual peer outreach, street hustling, sex work

Primary Care Use

The study participants were generally high-volume primary care users, with an average of 17.4 visits per person over the 4 year study period. Housing status was not routinely captured in the chart, with 67% of visits not documenting housing status at time of visit. Wounds, substance use, and infections were the most common reasons for seeking primary care. There was also a sizeable number of visits devoted to accessing social services (e.g. completing ODSP application). Notably, while primary care typically strives to provide preventative care and chronic disease management, very few visits were dedicated to this.

Table 2 Primary Care Visits 2018–2021 for people who experienced service restrictions in Hamilton, Ontario

Primary Care Visits (N = 330 visits, representing 19 study participants)		
Description	Number of Visits	
Average number of visits per person	17.4	
Minimum visits per person	3	
Maximum visits per person	Over 45	
Description	Number of Participants	
0 - 4 visits in study period	2	
5 - 12 visits in study period	7	
13 - 20 visits in study period	4	
21+ visits in study period	6	
Housing status at time of visit (N=279 visits*)	N	%*
Housed	13	4.7
Unsheltered homelessness	30	10.8
Sheltered homelessness	46	16.5
Not documented	189	67.7
Restricted from all shelters	1	0.4

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Reason for Visit (N=279 visits*)			
Category	Sub-Category	N	%*
Infections		53	13.5
	<i>Abscesses</i>	9	2.3
	<i>Endocarditis</i>	3	0.8
	<i>Osteomyelitis</i>	8	2.0
	<i>Other infections</i>	33	8.4
Substance Use Disorder		52	13.2
Wounds		44	11.2
Medications		40	10.2
Mental Health		34	8.7
Assistance with accessing social services		32	8.1
Pain		28	7.1
Other		23	5.9
Inflammation		18	4.6
Supportive Visits		15	3.8
Traumatic Injuries		14	3.6
Preventative Health		11	2.8
Headache		6	1.5
Dental Issues		6	1.5
Type 2 Diabetes		5	1.3
Gastrointestinal Issues		4	1.0
Hepatitis C		4	1.0
Shortness of Breath		2	0.5
Respiratory Issues		2	0.5

*representing a maximum of 25 visits reviewed per study participant, as described in the methods

*Does not add to 100% due to rounding

Emergency Department Use

Along with high primary care use, study participants used the emergency department frequently, with an average of 10.9 visits per person over the 4 year study period. In 10% of visits participants presented to the emergency department while in custody of police or correctional officers. There was a high rate of patient-initiated discharge either before or after being seen by the emergency room physician, at almost 14% of visits. Infections, traumatic injuries, and substance use were the most common reasons for visits, accounting for 65% of visits.

Table 3 Emergency Department Visits 2018–2021 for people who experienced service restriction in Hamilton, Ontario

Emergency Department Visits (N = 217 visits, representing 19 participants)			
Description		Number of Visits	
Average number of visits per person		10.95	
Minimum visits per person		2	
Maximum visits per person		Over 27	
Description		Number of Participants	
0 - 4 visits in study period		3	
5 - 12 visits in study period		10	
13 - 20 visits in study period		2	
21+ visits in study period		4	
Presented Form		N	%*
Walk-In		121	55.8
EMS		74	34.1
Brought in by police or correctional officers		22	10.0
Disposition		N	%*
Discharged home		149	68.7
Admitted to hospital		18	18.0
Discharged to custody of police or correctional officers		14	6.5
Discharged to shelter		6	2.8
Patient-initiated discharge after being seen by ERP*		26	12.0
Patient-initiated discharge before being seen by ERP*		4	1.8
Reason for Visit			
Category	Sub-category	N	%*
Substance Related		70	32.3
	<i>Substance Overdose</i>	33	15.2
	<i>Substance Abuse</i>	24	11.1
	<i>Seeking Detox</i>	5	2.3
	<i>Withdrawal</i>	8	3.7

Continued on next page

Infections		41	18.9
	<i>Abcesses</i>	16	2.8
	<i>Skin and Soft Tissue Infections</i>	5	7.4
	<i>Endocarditis</i>	2	0.9
	<i>Osteomyelitis</i>	2	0.9
	<i>Pneumonia</i>	5	2.3
	<i>MRSA (location/type not specified)</i>	5	2.3
	<i>Other infections</i>	5	2.3
Traumatic Injuries		30	13.8
Pain		21	9.7
Mood Disturbances		14	6.5
	<i>Depression</i>	3	1.1
	<i>Suicidal Ideation</i>	5	2.3
	<i>Behavioural Issues</i>	6	2.8
Dental Issues		10	4.6
Inflammation		10	4.6
Altered LOC		9	4.2
Wounds		8	3.7
Hyperglycemia		5	2.3
Headache		4	1.8
Constipation		1	0.5
Nausea/Vomiting		1	0.5
Seizure		1	0.5
Shortness of Breath		1	0.5

*ERP = Emergency Room Physician

+Does not add up to 100% due to rounding

Hospitalizations

Hospital admissions occurred in 16% of emergency department visits. Again, there are high rates of patient-initiated discharge following hospital admission, at just over 14% of admissions. Only 5.7% of admissions are for substance related reasons, which represents less than 3% of substance related emergency department visits. The most common reasons for admission were traumatic injuries and infections.

Table 4 Inpatient Hospital Admissions 2018–2021 for people who experienced service restriction in Hamilton, Ontario

Inpatient Hospital Admissions (N = 35 visits, representing 19 study participants)			
Description		Number of Visits	
Average number of visits per person		4	
Minimum visits per person		0	
Maximum visits per person		10	
Description		Number of Participants	
0 visits in study period		8	
1 – 4 visits in study period		10	
5 + visits in study period		1	
Disposition		N	%⁺
Home		13	37.1
Jail		1	2.9
Patient-initiated discharge		5	14.3
Shelter		15	42.9
Transitional care bed		1	2.9
Reason for Visit			
Category	Sub-Category	N	%⁺
Traumatic Injuries		11	31.4
Infections		11	31.4
	Pneumonia	1	2.9
	Skin and Soft Tissue Infections	4	11.4
	Endocarditis	4	11.4
	MRSA (location/type not specified)	2	5.7
	Infection (not otherwise specified)	1	2.9
Pain		3	8.6
Gynecologic Procedures		3	8.6
Substance Related		2	5.7
Hyperglycemia		1	2.9
Inflammation		1	2.9
Seizure		1	2.9

⁺Does not add to 100% due to rounding

Qualitative Results – Reflexive Thematic Analysis

We developed five themes describing participants' experiences of service restrictions and their consequences. The themes are interrelated and presented in no particular order:

1. Losing your home shouldn't mean losing your humanity
2. Where am I supposed to go?
3. The snakes and ladders of service restriction
4. Constantly criminalized
5. Harnessing the wisdom of community

1. Losing your home shouldn't mean losing your humanity

Participants' humanity is threatened when experiencing homelessness. Shelter users often described feeling labeled, dehumanized, and treated without compassion when discussing their interactions with shelter staff. Some identified that there is an apparent lack of staffing, training, and sensitivity towards those accessing shelters.

“Because homeless, that label itself puts under, 15 more labels right underneath that just because of that one label. So from all that. Then we're no longer looked at as people. When you're not dealing with human life, we're not looked at as people and you're not dealing with life itself, you're now just a number, or just an addiction problem, or a mental health problem, or a disability. And all these different things. And we're not looked at as people anymore, so we don't get treated like a person.” (Interviewee 9)

Similar feelings of dehumanization were felt among participants when accessing healthcare, with some PWUD expressing that they faced stigma from healthcare professionals. As a direct result of being treated differently based on their substance use, people avoided seeking healthcare.

“Honestly I don't. I don't. And that's what ended up happening is that I ended up getting so sick from not going, because when I did go I wasn't looked at properly. And I got sick. But then I got so sick, because every time I go I would just get looked at, and so it would be, oh well, it's got to be because he's dope sick or whatever. And that's not the case, but that's because what they already think they know.” (Interviewee 9)

“Instantly the nurses absolutely are judgmental...we have an addiction, yes. Sorry. But you know, like we're not animals, we're not monsters. You know, like we say, you don't know what we've been through. So, yeah, they've got to stop being so judgmental.” (Interviewee 7)

“If you're homeless they just want to rush you through as quick as they can and get you out the door. They don't want you in there. You're in there and clogging up their beds and clogging up the system, so they just try to push you out the door.” (Interviewee 6)

Participants expressed that their physical and psychological safety was constantly challenged and threatened. There is a perpetual cycle of trauma from the constant loss and theft of belongings while homeless or following a service restriction. These physical conditions caused or worsened existing mental health, physical health, and substance use related conditions for some shelter users.

“Affected my mental health more than anything else because you lose everything that you have when you’re service restricted. They steal it all. Whatever is there they throw it away somehow and then say they lost it—in most cases. And then you have to walk into the world again with the clothes on your back and try and make your way somehow with nothing. But it’s daunting.” (Interviewee 10)

“And I’m not really worried about that as much as I’m worried about housing because, you know, I still, I’m left with a very strange feeling at night when you’re not housed, eh. You don’t know who’s coming down the street. You don’t know what’s going to happen. This is going to happen, that, you know.” (Interviewee 8)

“Or, like stressed out because I get, like you were saying, like anxiety and stuff. Like, I get anxiety all the time because, like, it’s stressful when you don’t have a place to go so you’re—like for the day, you’re stressing out about where you’re going to sleep at night. And then when you don’t find a place, like, not knowing what’s gonna happen or how you’re going to, you know, like, get through the night and stuff like that.” (Interviewee 2)

Despite these physical and psychological conditions experienced while living on the streets, numerous participants feel safer on the streets than in a shelter. Participants described a lack of privacy, violence, and a jail-like environment that make shelters a stressful and uncomfortable place for them to access. In a shelter, there is a sense of constantly negotiating how to meet your needs and spend your time under surveillance of staff. There was a common undertone that human connection is the most important thing to feel a sense of home, which is lacking in the current shelter system.

“I’d say it was pretty much the same just because—I don’t know. I didn’t find the shelters any less stressful than like just being on the street, because it’s like the same type of people. It’s other, like people, strangers, that are on the street, that have, I don’t know, nothing and they, like, I guess, for some reason steal from other homeless people or, like, there’s always fights there and stuff like that and police.” (Interviewee 19)

“But I mean, keeping your things and your belongings, and taking them all over the place. And people steal and people don’t steal, and people go without things because people take things away from them, you know. It’s just kind of hard to start your life over until you’ve actually moved into a new home, you know.” (Interviewee 8)

“The most important thing that people need to realize is that human contact is the most important part of every condition. Without that, taking away the essential need for people to communicate and feel empathy for each other, or help share experiences, makes the experience lonely, sad, angry and eventually explosive. So, I think that would be the most important thing I think people should take out of this is to stop separating people. And I think public shelters would work a lot better, because then the staff would actually have an interest in what’s going on around them, and start caring about the people they’re helping. And maybe then they’d stand up and not let these service restrictions happen in the first place. Maybe saying, no, that’s bullshit. But right now, it’s more of a corporate model, so they just do what they’re told and because of that there’s no way staff can stand up either or they get fired—and everybody wants a job now.” (Interviewee 10)

Ultimately, study participants wanted a home, not a shelter bed.

"I am optimistic. I'm sure that I'm going to find a home. Like, maybe I'm tired of moving. I don't want to move all the time. I really don't want to start over again. You know, well, I mean I will have to start over, but I don't want to have to do it all the time, you know what I mean. I want to move somewhere and stay there. I want to stay there, I mean hopefully." (Interviewee 8)

Homelessness removed people from the bureaucratic systems of society and created legal barriers, which had implications when trying to re-enter the workforce. In addition to the limitations of not having a fixed address, other systematic barriers that prevent those without a home from accessing the workforce included not having a bank account and potentially having a criminal record. PWUD also expressed concern about stigma towards them if they wanted to enter the workforce, and the distress that current substance use could impact their performance in the workplace.

"Two years ago, I was working basically for myself...Like, what's the first thing that stops me from doing that today? Can only accept customers that are paying in cash. I'm unable to send fast e-transfer to people such as like a driver for gas money to come pick me up and take me to a job. No bank account, no e-transfers. You're less of a person. Unable to rent a vehicle, lease a vehicle—less a person, you know. Criminal record—you can't own a City registered business." (Interviewee 12)

2. Where am I supposed to go?

Being service restricted is not just the loss of a bed. Following a service restriction, participants are cut off from social and health services. For some, being service restricted increased barriers to accessing healthcare and increased their use of the emergency department. This was enacted by rules that limited access (e.g. service restricted from a shelter so could not see the doctor at the clinic in that shelter), difficulty accessing due to services being too far away from shelters they were restricted from (e.g. even if they were allowed to use the clinic at the location they had been service restricted from, they were now geographically too far away to practically access it), and internalized and external stigma following a service restriction.

"So any service they could forward, it sounds like they're restricting you, and they're not giving you access to any of it. So I mean to me, it sounds like they're shutting them down all across the board." (Interviewee 4) "But, really, it's that I was too embarrassed to go back and collect my things and find out if I can either get my methadone there, or whether I have to go back to the clinic and drop from a high dose that helps out a bit, to a low dose that I almost won't feel at all." (Interviewee 12)

"If you get service restricted from somewhere where, you know, it's comfortable for you, and then the only place you can go is somewhere where you're not comfortable going, you're basically guaranteed to be outside" (Interviewee 12)

With nowhere to go, people generally either joined encampments or were just floating around outside. Participants described how service restrictions directly contribute to the growth of encampments.

"I just gave up and I just pitched a tent and became a part of that community." (Interviewee 11)

"[service restriction] causes it to grow, and living out is better than nowhere." (Interviewee 12)

“Well, yeah. I was in a tent. Yeah. I was forced to leave too, just like the other ones were. And I didn’t think much of it then as I do now. I think of it now as like, they didn’t really push us around. They just said in a nice way, like, “You got to go.” And really, I didn’t see any need that we had to go, you know. It was just like a step going backwards all the time. We had to move, you know what I mean. Even though there was uncertainty of what you’d have left, by the next day because everything gets stolen. If it’s not nailed down, it’s gone, you know what I mean. So, it’s kind of hard to keep your things to yourself when you’re always having to move around all the time. I mean, it’s kind of like going backwards, I feel. And I don’t know, there should be an easier way to deal with the situation of these tents than just having to move all the time, you know what I mean.” (Interviewee 8)

The lack of access to basic necessities in encampments worsened health outcomes of encampment residents. For example, rates of contracting an infection increased, which was mirrored in the high frequency of visits for infections in primary care, ED and hospital admissions. Although several participants were reluctant to seek hospital-based care, they still represent a group with high healthcare utilization.

“Health was horrible. Every single person I came in contact with had some type of infection, sickness. And it was just—yeah, it was just running rife throughout the camps. Like, everybody was—I’m pretty sure you’ve seen it, everybody’s got infections, sores, cuts or whatever. You know, so the health was very, very bad.” (Interviewee 11)

Winter was identified as a particularly difficult and important time to be able to access shelter.

“Then I found myself trying to find a stairwell to stay in, because it was freezing. It was during the winter. So I ended running and sneaking into the Sheraton, downstairs into the basement parking lot, running to a stairwell before the security guards caught me and going to the stairwell that I know of that pumps out like hot air. I woke up to cops giving me a ticket, a \$70 ticket. And that’s the truth, right there. That was painful.” (Interviewee 19)

“But clearly, like, tell me what to do? What can I do? I can’t go here, here, here or here. It’s minus 15 out and you guys won’t let anyone sit inside your staircase door at the [Shelter] or whatever like that, right. And, yeah, light a fire and the firemen will come and put it out and tell you not to light another fire. So, I mean, there’s very little help and offering options, you know. Because for the most time, or for the most part, it’s because people are getting service restricted that there’s already a negativity towards them for whatever they’ve done to cause that, right.” (Interviewee 12)

3. The snakes and ladders of service restriction

There was a common experience among participants that the process and rules of service restriction were arbitrary and unjust. Participants felt rules were applied at random depending on the individual shelter staff implementing them. This contributed to the growing mistrust between shelter staff and users, and a sense among participants that there is a misuse of power by staff. It often felt as if the reason for being restricted was not made clear to shelter users. Participants felt that rules were unrealistic, and it was impossible to abide by them especially if you are a person who uses drugs.

“There’s like women out there that do sex work, and they would lose their bed

because they weren't home, because they had to make their money at night, which makes it really hard for that person.” (Interviewee 13)

There is a need for transparency regarding service restrictions and appropriate processes for appeal and mediation. It was suggested that conflict resolution, mediation, and meaningful involvement of those with lived or living experiences could be ways to improve the current service restrictions processes.

“Offering an appeal process. Being clear on the reasons why, and showing the rules that were broken, and showing where you recognize the rules that was broken, or you read these rules, or they were explained to you... Be clear, give warnings, have a protocol for it that they have to follow. A couple of warnings. And the warnings themselves can be appealed. Because I've been tricked by that too and kicked out. And they just say that they warned you about something that they didn't warn you about.” (Interviewee 10)

“I think you could have more meetings, more engagements, more events, more time that we can work with each other and go over (indiscernible) maybe sometimes that they said, you know, they (indiscernible) certain goals and ways to deal with the clientele, specifically, (indiscernible) have some of the clients there at those meetings.” (Interviewee 4)

“Time out. To have somebody who's not working with them and working for them, you've got to have somebody in the middle, you know, like a mediator, who's going to be fair and not working with the police and not working with the system and not working with any of them; just a regular person who could, you know, empathize, sympathize with people, and you know. That would help a lot. I think that would make a big difference, man. That would be it. And not have them make that decision, that final call, you know.” (Interviewee 11)

Substance use was a common reason for service restrictions, and attempting to avoid service restriction created a heightened risk environment for PWUD.³¹ Abstinence-based rules regarding substance use in shelters forced PWUD to choose either avoiding shelters altogether and staying outside or using shelters and trying to avoid service restriction by hiding their substance use. For some participants, service restriction forced them back to the streets and precipitated relapse to substance use or increased substance use. This was reflected in a high frequency of ED visits specifically for substance use issues. Although hospitals may not be the ideal or preferred setting to receive substance use care, low admission rates after presentation with substance use issues suggest that people seeking care are not offered inpatient admission in instances where it may be beneficial.

“Well, maybe. Like, I guess being more understanding or like lenient when it comes to people getting service restricted for reasons related to their addiction and stuff. Because that's, like, a reason why people get service restricted a lot of the time too, is because they get caught using or they get caught with drugs and stuff.” (Interviewee 2)

“I'm like, “You have no idea how to deal with people. I'm not using you as a crutch or an excuse, but I'll tell you right now, I've got money in my wallet. I'm gonna go out there. It's cold. I'm gonna probably end up in an abandoned building, and there's gonna be dope everywhere and I'm probably gonna relapse. I hope you feel good about yourself.” “this one [shelter staff], she'd done it to three different people. And my one friend relapsed using alcohol, this other one relapsed using crystal meth; all for the same reason because this woman was on a high horse and kicked us out for nothing, just stupid, childish things.” (Interviewee 7)

4. Constantly criminalized

Despite not a single question in the interview guide about criminalization or incarceration, almost every research participant identified that policing, incarceration, and criminalization affected their lives and their health. Often these interactions with the justice system were a threat or misuse of police involvement during a service restriction.

“Then, I knew the cops were going to get called, everything, because I watched it all play out. And so then I was arrested. And they made sure that I wasn’t getting out. They tried to make sure that I got whatever. That shelter made sure, right.” (Interviewee 9)

Some participants noted that being service restricted then pushed them into public spaces where they were under surveillance from police and more likely to be stopped or picked up on charges. Police, parole, and bail conditions could also restrict people from certain geographic areas, making it even harder to access essential services when service restricted.

“Like, my probation doesn’t allow me to go 50 metres near that [name] building across from the [Shelter]. So I don’t want to go to the [Shelter], I’m going to jail, you know what I mean. I’m only permitted there between 10:00 and 1:00 o’clock, you know what I mean. So, I’m basically crossing an imaginary line and every time I do and I’m caught, I’m being thrown in jail for it, you know what I mean. So it’s like, you know what, not only was I being restricted at the shelters, I was kind of like, the police were kind of pushing and bullying me around, telling me I can’t be anywhere between Hughson, Ferguson, Cannon and King William. Do you know how big of a perimeter that is?” (Interviewee 8)

There was also frequent police presence when accessing healthcare. Some reported avoiding seeking care due to police presence in these settings. Others described this in a matter-of-fact way, simply noting it as a feature of accessing healthcare in hospitals or via emergency medical services (EMS).

“But it wasn’t because I was violent or anything. It’s just like once they found out I was wanted, they had to pretty much stay with me like the whole time I was in the hospital. And I was there for, like six days. So for the first three days, it was like two Hamilton police, like cops. Then they transferred my, I guess, like, possession or responsibility of me to the Barton jail guards. And I had to wear a jumpsuit and like shackles and handcuffs in the hospital the whole time. But then, like, on the morning of when I got discharged, I had court, so they brought me into court and I got released on bail, anyways. So I never actually went to jail. But, like, the whole time I was in the hospital, I had like an orange jumpsuit and I had to walk around cuffed and shackled with two guards, one on each side of me, the whole time, anywhere I walked.” (Interviewee 2)

5. Harnessing the wisdom of community

Many research participants called for a transparent and consistent service restriction process that allowed for timely appeals and the involvement of a neutral third party. Participants noted the need for more practical approaches to substance use in shelters, more privacy in shelters, and a range of shelters for different ages (e.g. shelters for older adults), and family structures (e.g. shelters for couples without children). Participants thought there should always be somewhere for people to go, where they are directed to at the time of service restriction and not left to locate on their own.

“They shouldn’t like make these rules and have them enforced by these people who have no idea what’s going on. They should have like a intermediate person, like someone, like a mediator, right; like someone in the middle, to really lead, like, not bias and stuff and really look at the whole situation and make a decision then; not just have a person say, “You did this, so you’re done. That’s it. No discussion. You’re out of here.” You know what I mean? Because it’s heartbreaking, man, you know, guys getting restricted for stupid things, and that’s it, there’s no option, they’re just, they’re done. And it’s pretty annoying” (Interviewee 7)

“Maybe have, like less crowded space with less people in, like, the dorm or whatever. Or like, I don’t know. I guess it’s not really possible to have, like, a private space because there’s a lot of people. I guess maybe, like, the best or the closest thing to having the least amount of people, rather than having like a dense amount of people in a small space. It’s like jail. It’s literally like jail.” (Interviewee 2)

“There should always be somewhere where you can go, you know. It shouldn’t be totally—in a city of this size, there shouldn’t be a person that’s totally restricted from everywhere. It’s minus 40 in the winter.” (Interviewee 12)

Many study participants were involved in harm reduction informally (e.g., checking on friends while they were using or acquiring sterile drug use supplies to distribute to friends and shelter co-residents) and formally (e.g., volunteering with Keeping Six). Social determination of health invites us to think about how this community knowledge and action serves to resist and reduce the harm from both Canada’s and shelters’ prohibitionist drug policies.

“I’m involved with harm reduction because I believe it saves lives, the people... Yeah, like I had a bunch; a package, a ten-pack, a two-pack, whatever, and anybody that required them, I would just hand them out to them, because that’s what I do. And what do you call it—kits, and whatever, the Nalox health kit.” (Interviewee 1)

Most participants called for alternatives that would enable PWUD to safely and reliably access shelters, including changing abstinence-based rules to ones that recognize the reality of substance use and allow shelter users to have and use drugs. People described the safety improvements they saw with safer drug use spaces in some shelters and called for these to be widely implemented. A few participants called for both sober and wet shelters, because people could not maintain their abstinence from substance use when desired given the rampant substance use in shelters. This responds to the high rates of substance-use related hospital presentations we observed in the chart review data.

“Being more understanding or like lenient when it comes to people getting service restricted for reasons related to their addiction and stuff. Because that’s, like, a reason why people get service restricted a lot of the time too, is because they get caught using or they get caught with drugs and stuff.” (Interviewee 2)

“This one has one, has a safe injection site in it and it’s been a lot better over there for a lot of the females than it was before.” (Interviewee 17)

“I think every place should have a safe site for people that use.” (Interviewee 16)

One participant noted he wanted a shift away from harm reduction alone towards more robust treatment options.

“Well, they could have like programs involved to help them get better instead of just shoving harm reduction and supply in their faces and just saying, “Go ahead, use. Use. Keep using. Go ahead.” They could have, try some type of program to help people understand why they’re in that position, why they’re in that predicament and what happened, where they went wrong and how to make life better. How to, you know stop that addiction problem or disease or whatever it is.” (Interviewee 11)

Study participants reiterated longstanding calls for healthcare to be non-judgmental, accessible, and meet people where they are at. This contrasted with the experiences they described particularly in hospitals. Participants noted the importance of street outreach conducted by clinics and physicians. While physical healthcare was more accessible, except for pain management, most participants spoke to a lack of accessible mental health resources, including psychiatric care, counseling, residential treatment, social workers, and other non-pharmacologic therapies. Some positive healthcare experiences were mentioned, in the context of the exception that proves the rule in hospitals. Medication access was generally reliable. Many also noted the importance of the Shelter Health Network in providing accessible and reliable healthcare.

“Just do outreach. More outreach and more and more showing up where people are at instead of having them to come to you, right. And so that be the big thing.” (Interviewee 6)

“They do a lot. I’ve watched what they do. They’ve done everything, from giving tents, to shoes, clothing, you know, medical aid, you know... I told the doctor, I said, “I’m getting healthy because a lot of good people are helping me,” I told him. I said, “Hell, not on my own.” (Interviewee 8)

Despite the hardships, challenges, and mistreatment, there was a resounding sense of strong community among those surviving homelessness and service restrictions. Those interviewed described themselves as caring, and able to cope as a community with challenges despite a system that is working against them.

“All kinds, like good things, I guess you could say. Well, you know, I still help people and give the shirt off my own back. and I’m homeless. and have nothing. And somebody that has less than what I have, I still give. And that’s what’s most people ever give.” (Interviewee 8)

Discussion

This exploratory research project used a qualitative approach contextualized by chart review data to better understand the experiences of shelter users who are service restricted. We aimed to describe this subset of shelter users, explore their healthcare use and health conditions, and better understand their unique experiences. Kerman et al's study identified victimisation and criminalisation as predictors of service restriction in Canadian settings³², while US-based research on unsheltered homelessness more broadly determined that violence and victimisation were major deterrents to accessing shelter.^{33,34} We similarly found that individuals who are service restricted commonly experience victimisation and criminalisation both inside and outside of shelters. These experiences contributed to worsening physical and mental health and exacerbation of substance use-related problems among study participants. Promoting health among people who are service restricted must therefore address the underlying drivers of victimisation and criminalisation. This includes expanding access to stable, permanent, non-congregate housing rather than congregate shelters where conditions are ripe for violence³⁵; and adopting non-policing-based approaches, such as non-violent crisis intervention and restorative justice to address unsafe behaviours in shelters.

We observed that service restriction often led directly to unsheltered homelessness and being disconnected from key health and social services, while intensifying substance use. This reinforces findings in Kerman et al's study of antecedents and consequences of service restriction³⁶, and additionally highlights how this negatively affected participants' health—for example, by increasing the risk of infectious diseases. Studies conducted by Kerman et al. in 2022 and 2024 also reported regional differences in service restriction, pointing to factors beyond the individual level that determined risk of service restriction.^{37,38} We identified specific organisational and community-level factors that shape those risks within the Hamilton context from the perspective of service users, including the rigid enforcement of abstinence-based substance use policies and arbitrary application of service restriction policies. This speaks to the need to support and incentivise action at the organisational and community levels in order to improve the health of people who are service restricted, rather than merely supporting service restricted individuals themselves.

Eve Tuck's concept of Suspending Damage called us to go beyond merely documenting "peoples' pain and brokenness to hold those in power accountable for their oppression"³⁹ to consider how people who have been service restricted are navigating their own ways to better individual and community health. Despite being neglected by systems and society, participants found strength and support in taking care of themselves and each other. Participants valued, practiced, and promoted harm reduction to guard against the risks associated with the toxic drug supply and shelter policies that increased this risk by pushing drug use out of sight.

Participants had many ideas for a better system because of experiencing the current limitations and shortfalls that exist. They called for policies and processes to be more transparent, accountable and with an accessible appeal process. They also recommended a more pragmatic approach to substance use in shelters, which could reduce both the frequency of service restriction and harms related to substance use. In Hamilton, two local initiatives have surfaced to address these concerns: a time-limited safe supply and supervised drug use program operated for 4 weeks during a COVID-19 outbreak at a men's shelter⁴⁰, and an ongoing

supervised injection space at a women's shelter⁴¹. Similar low-barrier models are reported in North American literature, though they are limited in number.^{42,43} Available evidence suggests these interventions decrease drug-related harms, improve access to healthcare, uphold dignity and autonomy, and foster stronger relationships between staff and service users.^{44,45,46} Supervised drug consumption sites, in particular, reduce the frequency of substance use-related incidents requiring emergency medical care.⁴⁷

Although we did not ask specific questions about criminalization, participants frequently described the threat of police and arrest was used to enforce service restrictions, deterred them from seeking healthcare, and was a common experience in everyday life. The Latin American concept of Social Determination of Health⁴⁸ offers a framework for understanding how the structures of policing and criminalization drive homelessness and health disparities. People lose their homes and jobs during incarceration; police target these same groups of people once they are service restricted and pushed into outdoor public spaces; and the threat of arrest and detention by police in hospitals acts as a deterrent to accessing healthcare. This further intersects with the racism, colonization, ableism, and other forms of oppression that determine who is over-policed, over-incarcerated and excluded or harmed by healthcare in the first place.

As a research team, we share a commitment to social justice and harm reduction. Social justice promotes equality and solidarity, understands and values human rights, and recognises the dignity of every individual.⁴⁹ Harm reduction 'focuses on positive change and on working with people without judgement, coercion, discrimination or requiring that people stop using drugs as a precondition of support.'⁵⁰ For example, our values pointed our attention towards how dignity was or was not experienced by participants when accessing shelters or healthcare, or how abstinence from substance use was or was not a prerequisite for accessing shelter or health-care services. Quality and trustworthiness were further enhanced by having multiple investigators involved in the RTA; drawing on our experiences of implementing, experiencing and caring for people facing

service restrictions to ask the right questions and interpret the context of participant responses; and using chart review data to triangulate against the interview data and RTA.⁵¹

We see our positionality as a strength of our research and part of our accountability to study participants and the broader communities of people deprived of housing and PWUD in Hamilton. While our diverse lived experiences and perspectives enriched the qualitative analysis and strengthened the validity of our findings, we recognize that some decision makers or stakeholders who do not share our values may question the validity of our results. By being transparent about our values and reflecting on them throughout the research process, we aim to make clear how they shaped our results so that readers can consider for themselves how this shapes their interpretation of our work.

Study Limitations

We asked participants what communities they identified belonging to and about the health of those communities. We considered the social determination of health in generating our themes. Despite this, because of insufficient thickness in the qualitative data⁵², we were not able to adequately speak to the specific impact of race, colonization, gender, sexual orientation, or gender identity in our themes.

While qualitative research does not seek to be generalizable, we acknowledge that the study sample for the chart review portion of the research may not be representative of all people who have been service restricted in Hamilton. Because our recruitment included recruiting on outreach alongside Keeping Six Hamilton Harm Reduction Action League we were more likely to recruit PWUD. Thus, our chart review data is illustrative and exploratory.

We were also not able to access data on the dates of service restriction, so we could not compare health status or healthcare access during periods of service restriction to outside of those periods. Our data collection was limited to one primary care clinic group, and Hamilton based hospitals, so if people accessed care outside of these locations those data were not included in our analysis.

Implications for Policy, Practice and Research

Indirect Policy

1. All 3 levels of government (municipal, provincial, and federal) need to ensure that every person in Canada has access to safe, affordable, permanent housing, with appropriate supports as needed.
2. Harm reduction and treatment are complementary approaches that both require adequate planning, funding, and resources.
3. Investments are needed in infectious disease care, preventative care, substance use care, and chronic pain care targeted to people experiencing or at risk of housing deprivation.
4. Ontario Disability Support Program and Ontario Works should increase to reflect cost of living.
5. Reducing the presence of police and the threat of arrest, charges, and detention while accessing shelter and healthcare should be pursued to reduce barriers to accessing those life sustaining services.

Direct Policy

1. The City of Hamilton and shelter operators should offer pragmatic options for PWUD who are deprived of housing, including safer drug use spaces embedded in shelters, the ability to access sterile drug use supplies while in shelter, shelters designated for people who are actively using drugs or alcohol, and shelters designated for people seeking a sober living environment.
2. Service restriction policies should be clearly communicated, staff should be trained and resourced to implement it, there should be a timely appeals process, and data should be systematically collected on service restrictions and shared publicly for increased transparency and accountability.
3. No one should be service restricted if they have nowhere to go.

Practice

1. Shelter staff need to have the training, skills, and experience to provide people with resourced, humanized, non-judgmental care and services. This should be coupled with adequate staff support, compensation, and accountability mechanisms to implement and sustain this approach to care.
2. Better tracking of housing status in healthcare would assist in better evaluation of the health status and needs of people deprived of housing and how it correlates with changes in their housing status.
3. The City of Hamilton should use HIFIS data to understand patterns and consequences of service restriction.

Research

1. This project lays the groundwork for research that expands beyond our sample of research participants.
2. Future research may compare those who have not been service restricted with those who have, to determine if what we found in our project was unique to those who have been service restricted or generalizable to everyone experiencing housing deprivation in Hamilton, Ontario.
3. Future research should seek to further integrate community engaged and community driven research methods.
4. Understanding the social determination of health and the role that systems of oppression and resistance to oppression play in the health of people who are service restricted is only cursorily explored here and is worthy of subsequent research.

Knowledge Translation

Study results were shared at a community barbecue and a stakeholder results sharing workshop. The barbecue event was advertised on street outreach with Keeping Six, at Keeping Six drop-in and HAMSMaRT clinics, and via other groups that serve people deprived of housing in Hamilton. It was held July 7, 2023 at lunchtime in J.C. Beemer park. A few days before the barbecue, CB stopped by the encampment at the park to drop off food and invite encampment residents to the barbecue. Approximately 40 people attended and heard about the research project and findings. We distributed a 2-page handout explaining the qualitative results (Appendix C). People were invited to share their feedback on the results. Generally, the results resonated with people, but they felt there was not enough emphasis on the need for permanent, safe, affordable, accessible housing. People shared many stories of renoviction (the eviction of a tenant from a unit for the landlord to undertake repairs or renovations for the purpose of renting the unit out at a higher rate) and illegal eviction, and expressed that they did not want a shelter bed – they wanted a home. Low social assistance rates (Ontario Disability Support Payments and Ontario Works payments) were also identified as a major problem that was not highlighted in the results we shared with attendees. People felt it was good just to take up space together around this issue. A few people currently living outdoors talked about wanting to organize homeless people to rally at City Hall.

The stakeholder results sharing workshop was held a few weeks later on August 2, 2023 at David Braley Health Sciences Centre. The agenda is attached as Appendix D. The workshop was invitation-only, to ensure that a wide range of health, social service, and municipal stakeholders were in attendance. The organizations represented can be found in Appendix E. The event fostered a robust discussion, covering the wide-ranging factors influencing housing deprivation, shelter operation, municipal decision making, and service restriction; along with possible legal, community-based, organizational, and political remedies to housing access and deprivation. While some time was spent discussing service restriction and improvements to the process, larger systemic issues were the primary focus of the conversation.

In August 2025, an original research article was published in [BMJ Public Health](#). The article is published open-access, in the spirit of ensuring our research findings are accessible to the community.

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Appendices

Appendix A– Interview Guide

Preamble:

This study is intended to better understand the relationship between health and service restrictions from emergency shelters. Anything we discuss during this interview is confidential and will only be used for research purposes. Nothing you say will be shared with the hospital, healthcare providers, shelter, or police in a way that can identify you. If you do not feel comfortable answering a question, you can choose to skip it.

For the purposes of our interview, an emergency shelter is temporary overnight accommodation provided by an agency for someone without another place to stay. A service restriction is being officially banned or blocked from accessing the emergency shelter for a period of time.

Questions:

1. Tell me a little bit about yourself. Who are you? How would someone else describe you if they were introducing you to me?
2. We're interested in the health of not just individuals, but groups of people. Are there any groups or communities of people you identify as being part of? (if required, you can prompt with "for example, part of the queer community, part of the Black community, or part of the encampments community") (If yes) what groups or communities are these?
3. How long have you been using or trying to use emergency shelters in Hamilton?
4. When you are trying to access an emergency shelter, are you ever trying to access it with someone else? For example, a partner or sibling?
 - a. (If yes) who do you usually try to access shelter with?
5. How many times have you been service restricted from an emergency shelter, or told you cannot return to an emergency shelter for a period of time?
6. What is the longest service restriction from an emergency shelter you've ever had?
7. Have you ever been service restricted from all of the emergency shelters in Hamilton?
 - a. (If yes) for how long were you service restricted from all of the emergency shelters in Hamilton?
8. Tell me about your health.
 - a. Do you have any physical health problems – for example heart problems, breathing problems, or pain problems?
 - b. (If yes) Can you describe these problems for me?
 - c. Do you have any mental health problems – for example mood problems, personality problems, problems with psychosis, or substance use problems?
 - d. (If yes) Can you describe these problems for me?
 - e. Where do you usually go when you have a health problem? For example – a family doctor, a shelter health clinic, a nurse practitioner, or the emergency department.

Note to interviewer: if the participant discloses suicidal ideation, please provide them with information on seeking help. This could include the crisis text line (anyone in Canada can text the word HOME to 686868 to be connected 24/7 to a live crisis responder <https://www.crisistextline.ca/>), attending the

emergency department at St Joseph's Hospital at 50 Charlton Ave East, or calling the Barrett Centre 905-529-7878 which offers 24/7 emergency support in Hamilton and crisis shelter beds (<https://goodshepherdcentres.ca/services/barrett-centre-for-crisis-support/>). You can also contact the co-investigator Claire Bodkin at XXX-XXX-XXXX for support.

9. I want you to pick one time that you were service restricted from a shelter in Hamilton. I am going to ask you a whole bunch of questions about that experience to try and learn from your story.
 - a. Can you tell me a little bit about what happened?
 - b. Were you informed of why you were service restricted?
 - i. (If yes) Why were you service restricted?
 - ii. (If no) Why do you think you were service restricted?
 - c. Were you informed of how long you were service restricted for?
 - i. (If yes) How long were you restricted for?
 - ii. (If no) Do you know now how long you were service restricted for?
 - d. Were you informed of the rules around service restrictions, and how you could appeal or dispute the service restriction?
 - i. (If yes) what information were you given? Was it written or just told to you?
 - e. Where did you end up going after you were service restricted?
10. Now I'm going to ask you some questions about how being service restricted during the time you just told me about affected your health.
 - a. How did being service restricted affect your health? This includes your physical health and your mental health.
 - b. Do you think you used the emergency department more, less, or the same when you were service restricted?
 - c. Did you have any trouble seeing a family doctor or going to a walk in clinic when you were service restricted?
 - d. Did you have any trouble taking your medications when you were service restricted?
11. Now I'm going to ask you some questions about what shelters can do to improve the health and well-being of people who experience service restrictions. This doesn't have to be limited to just during the period of time that someone is service restricted.
 - a. What could a shelter do to make the experience of being in a shelter better for your health and well-being?
 - b. What could a shelter do to make the experience of being service restricted better for your health and well-being?
 - c. What could a shelter do to minimize any negative effects that service restrictions have on the health and well-being of someone who uses drugs or alcohol?
 - d. Thinking about the times you have been service restricted, how would you have wanted the shelter to respond differently?
 - e. What would you suggest the shelter staff do in a similar situation in the future?
 - f. What may have made a difference in your experience of the service restriction?
12. Now I'm going to ask you some questions about what healthcare providers and healthcare systems can do to improve the health of people who experience service restrictions. This doesn't have to be limited to just during the period of time that someone is service restricted.

- a. What could healthcare workers like doctors or nurses outside of the hospital do to improve the health of people who experience service restrictions?
 - b. What could healthcare workers like doctors or nurses inside the hospital do to improve the health of people who experience service restrictions?
 - c. What could healthcare systems like clinics or labs outside of the hospital do to improve the health of people who experience service restrictions?
 - d. What could healthcare systems like hospitals and emergency departments do to improve the health of people who experience service restrictions?
13. (If they identified communities or groups they are part of in question 2) Earlier you identified that you are part of _____ community.
- a. How would you describe the health of the _____ community in Hamilton?
 - b. How do service restrictions affect the health of the _____ community in Hamilton?
 - c. What needs to change to minimize the harm that service restrictions have on the health of the _____ community in Hamilton?
14. We want to capture some basic information about who we are interviewing. If you are comfortable, do you mind sharing the following information?
- a. How old are you?
 - b. How would you describe your sexual identity? (if required, you can prompt with “for example, gay, queer, or straight”)
 - c. How would you describe your gender identity? (if required, you can prompt with “for example, transgender, non-binary, or man”)
 - d. How would you describe your racial identity? (if required, you can prompt with “for example, Black, Indigenous, or Brown”)
 - e. How would you describe your ethnic or national identity? (if required, you can prompt with “for example, Mohawk, Chinese, or Irish”)
 - f. How do you make money? (if required, you can prompt with “for example, ODSP, working as a restaurant server, or sex work”)
 - g. Did you grow up in Hamilton?
 - i. (If no) where did you grow up?

Thanks so much for sharing all of this information with me today! When this study is done, we will share the final report on the HAMSMaRT website and at a community meeting. If you have shared your contact information with us, we can make sure you know how to read the report and join the meeting. Before we wrap up – is there anything else you think we should know about the relationship between health and service restrictions from emergencies.

Appendix B – Data Collection Form

Question	Question Type	Answers
Demographics		
ID	Textbox	<i>ID number between 1-20</i>
Gender	Dropdown	1, Man 2, Woman 3, Transgender Man 4, Transgender Woman 5, Non-binary 6, Not found in chart
Sex	Dropdown	1, Male 2, Female 3, Non-binary 4, Not found in chart
Source of Income	Multi Check	1, Employment Income 2, Self-employed, 3, Ontario Disabilities Support Program (ODSP) 4, Employment Insurance 5, Pension Income 6, Guaranteed Income Supplement (GIS) 7, Ontario Works 8, Workplace Safety and Insurance Board (WSIB) 9, Non-government support 10, Other 11, No Income 12, Not found in chart
Service Restrictions		
Service Restriction documented in chart	Radio	1, Yes 2, No
If yes, service restriction #1	Textbox	<i>Location, reason, length, narrative text if documented</i>
If yes, service restriction #2	Textbox	<i>Location, reason, length, narrative text if documented</i>
If yes, service restriction #3	Textbox	<i>Location, reason, length, narrative text if documented</i>
Emergency Department Visits		
Has this individual been to the Emergency Department between January 1 2018 and December 31 2021?	Radio	1, Yes 2, No
If yes, how many Emergency Department visits between January 1 2018 and December 31 2021 were documented in the chart?	Textbox	<i>Number between 1-10</i>
Primary reason for Emergency Department visit #1	Textbox	
Other issues present at time of Emergency Department #1	Textbox	
Admitted from	Multiple Choice	1, Walk-In 2, EMS 3, Brought in by authorities 4, Other
Discharged disposition	Multiple Choice	1, Discharged 2, Admitted to hospital 3, Other

Continued on next page

If other, describe	Textbox	
Primary reason for Emergency Department visit #2	Textbox	
Other issues present at time of Emergency Department #2	Textbox	
Admitted from	Multiple Choice	1, Walk-In 2, EMS 3, Brought in by authorities 4, Other
Discharged disposition	Multiple Choice	1, Discharged 2, Admitted to hospital 3, Other
If other, describe	Textbox	
Primary reason for Emergency Department visit #3	Textbox	
Other issues present at time of Emergency Department #3	Textbox	
Admitted from	Multiple Choice	1, Walk-In 2, EMS 3, Brought in by authorities 4, Other
Discharged disposition	Multiple Choice	1, Discharged 2, Admitted to hospital 3, Other
If other, describe	Textbox	
Primary reason for Emergency Department visit #4	Textbox	
Other issues present at time of Emergency Department #4	Textbox	
Admitted from	Multiple Choice	1, Walk-In 2, EMS 3, Brought in by authorities 4, Other
Discharged disposition	Multiple Choice	1, Discharged 2, Admitted to hospital 3, Other
If other, describe	Textbox	
Primary reason for Emergency Department visit #5	Textbox	
Other issues present at time of Emergency Department #5	Textbox	
Admitted from	Multiple Choice	1, Walk-In 2, EMS 3, Brought in by authorities 4, Other
Discharged disposition	Multiple Choice	1, Discharged 2, Admitted to hospital 3, Other
If other, describe	Textbox	
Primary reason for Emergency Department visit #6	Textbox	
Other issues present at time of Emergency Department #6	Textbox	
Admitted from	Multiple Choice	1, Walk-In 2, EMS 3, Brought in by authorities 4, Other
Discharged disposition	Multiple Choice	1, Discharged 2, Admitted to hospital 3, Other
If other, describe	Textbox	
Primary reason for Emergency Department visit #7	Textbox	
Other issues present at time of Emergency Department #7	Textbox	

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Admitted from	Multiple Choice	1, Walk-In 2, EMS 3, Brought in by authorities 4, Other
Discharged disposition	Multiple Choice	1, Discharged 2, Admitted to hospital 3, Other
If other, describe	Textbox	
Primary reason for Emergency Department visit #8	Textbox	
Other issues present at time of Emergency Department #8	Textbox	
Admitted from	Multiple Choice	1, Walk-In 2, EMS 3, Brought in by authorities 4, Other
Discharged disposition	Multiple Choice	1, Discharged 2, Admitted to hospital 3, Other
If other, describe	Textbox	
Primary reason for Emergency Department visit #9	Textbox	
Other issues present at time of Emergency Department #9	Textbox	
Admitted from	Multiple Choice	1, Walk-In 2, EMS 3, Brought in by authorities 4, Other
Discharged disposition	Multiple Choice	1, Discharged 2, Admitted to hospital 3, Other
If other, describe	Textbox	
Primary reason for Emergency Department visit #10	Textbox	
Other issues present at time of Emergency Department #10	Textbox	
Admitted from	Multiple Choice	1, Walk-In 2, EMS 3, Brought in by authorities 4, Other
Discharged disposition	Multiple Choice	1, Discharged 2, Admitted to hospital 3, Other
If other, describe	Textbox	
Hospital Admissions		
Has this individual been to the hospital between January 1 2018 and December 31 2021?	Radio	1, Yes 2, No
If yes, how many hospital visits between January 1 2018 and December 31 2021 were documented in the chart?	Textbox	<i>Number between 1-10</i>
Primary reason for hospital admission #1	Textbox	
Other issues present at time of hospital admission #1	Textbox	
Admitted from	Multiple Choice	1, From Emergency Department 2, Planned admission 3, Transfer from other hospital 4, Other
Discharged to	Textbox	
Primary reason for hospital admission #2	Textbox	

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Other issues present at time of hospital admission #2	Textbox	
Admitted from	Multiple Choice	1, From Emergency Department 2, Planned admission 3, Transfer from other hospital 4, Other
Discharged to	Textbox	
Primary reason for hospital admission #3	Textbox	
Other issues present at time of hospital admission #3	Textbox	
Admitted from	Multiple Choice	1, From Emergency Department 2, Planned admission 3, Transfer from other hospital 4, Other
Discharged to	Textbox	
Primary reason for hospital admission #4	Textbox	
Other issues present at time of hospital admission #4	Textbox	
Admitted from	Multiple Choice	1, From Emergency Department 2, Planned admission 3, Transfer from other hospital 4, Other
Discharged to	Textbox	
Primary reason for hospital admission #5	Textbox	
Other issues present at time of hospital admission #5	Textbox	
Admitted from	Multiple Choice	1, From Emergency Department 2, Planned admission 3, Transfer from other hospital 4, Other
Discharged to	Textbox	
Primary reason for hospital admission #6	Textbox	
Other issues present at time of hospital admission #6	Textbox	
Admitted from	Multiple Choice	1, From Emergency Department 2, Planned admission 3, Transfer from other hospital 4, Other
Discharged to	Textbox	
Primary reason for hospital admission #7	Textbox	
Other issues present at time of hospital admission #7	Textbox	
Admitted from	Multiple Choice	1, From Emergency Department 2, Planned admission 3, Transfer from other hospital 4, Other
Discharged to	Textbox	
Primary reason for hospital admission #8	Textbox	

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Other issues present at time of hospital admission #8	Textbox	
Admitted from	Multiple Choice	1, From Emergency Department 2, Planned admission 3, Transfer from other hospital 4, Other
Discharged to	Textbox	
Primary reason for hospital admission #9	Textbox	
Other issues present at time of hospital admission #9	Textbox	
Admitted from	Multiple Choice	1, From Emergency Department 2, Planned admission 3, Transfer from other hospital 4, Other
Discharged to	Textbox	
Primary reason for hospital admission #10	Textbox	
Other issues present at time of hospital admission #10	Textbox	
Admitted from	Multiple Choice	1, From Emergency Department 2, Planned admission 3, Transfer from other hospital 4, Other
Discharged to	Textbox	
Diagnoses		
Infectious Diseases: Has this individual had a diagnosis of any infectious diseases between January 1 2018 and December 31 2021?	Radio	1, Yes 2, No
If yes, list	Textbox	
Psychiatric Illnesses: Has this individual had a diagnosis of any psychiatric illnesses between January 1 2018 and December 31 2021?	Radio	1, Yes 2, No
If yes, list	Textbox	
Substance Use or Misuse: Has this individual had a diagnosis of any substance abuse disorders between January 1 2018 and December 31 2021?	Radio	1, Yes 2, No
If yes, list	Textbox	
Has this individual had a visit due to substance intoxication, overdose, or withdrawal?	Radio	1, Yes 2, No
If yes, visit #1	Textbox	
If yes, visit #2	Textbox	
If yes, visit #3	Textbox	
If yes, visit #4	Textbox	
If yes, visit #5	Textbox	

Continued on next page

Cognitive Impairments: Has this individual had a diagnosis of any cognitive impairments between January 1 2018 and December 31 2021?	Radio	1, Yes 2, No
If yes, list	Textbox	
Foot Issues: Has this individual had a diagnosis of any foot issues between January 1 2018 and December 31 2021?	Radio	1, Yes 2, No
If yes, list	Textbox	
Chronic Cardiorespiratory Diseases: Has this individual had a diagnosis of any chronic cardiorespiratory diseases between January 1 2018 and December 31 2021?	Radio	1, Yes 2, No
If yes, list	Textbox	
Chronic Metabolic Diseases: Has this individual had a diagnosis of any chronic metabolic diseases between January 1 2018 and December 31 2021?	Radio	1, Yes 2, No
If yes, list	Textbox	
Cancer: Has this individual had a diagnosis of cancer between January 1 2018 and December 31 2021?	Radio	1, Yes 2, No
If yes, list	Textbox	
Pregnancy: Has this individual been pregnant between January 1 2018 and December 31 2021?	Radio	1, Yes 2, No
If yes, how many times has this individual been pregnant between January 1 2018 and December 31 2021?	Textbox	
If yes, outcome of pregnancy #1	Multiple Choice	1, Therapeutic Abortion 2, Spontaneous Abortion 3, Still Birth 4, Preterm Birth 5, Term Birth 6, Other
If yes, outcome of pregnancy #2	Multiple Choice	1, Therapeutic Abortion 2, Spontaneous Abortion 3, Still Birth 4, Preterm Birth 5, Term Birth 6, Other
If yes, outcome of pregnancy #3	Multiple Choice	1, Therapeutic Abortion 2, Spontaneous Abortion 3, Still Birth 4, Preterm Birth 5, Term Birth 6, Other

Continued on next page

Reproductive Diseases: Has this individual had a diagnosis of any reproductive diseases between January 1 2018 and December 31 2021?	Radio	1, Yes 2, No
If yes, list	Textbox	
Unintentional Injuries: Has this individual had any unintentional injuries between January 1 2018 and December 31 2021?	Radio	1, Yes 2, No
If yes, list (Examples: burns, assaults resulting in stab wounds, fractures, head injuries, falls, motor vehicle accidents, heat/cold exposure injuries)	Textbox	
Other: Has this individual had any other diagnoses not otherwise stated between January 1 2018 and December 31 2021?	Radio	1, Yes 2, No
If yes, list	Textbox	

Category	ICD-10-CA-Category
Infection Diseases	See "Certain infectious and parasitic diseases" in ICD-10-CA
Psychiatric Illnesses	See all categories within "Mental and behavioural disorders" in ICD-10-CA except: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mental retardation • Disorders of psychological development • Any conditions with "Organic" related to dementia, Alzheimer's, TBI
Substance Use or Misuse	See notes in chart
Substance intoxication, overdose, or withdrawal	See notes in chart
Cognitive Impairments	See all categories within "Mental and behavioural disorders" in ICD-10-CA including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mental retardation • Disorders of psychological development • Any conditions with "Organic" related to dementia, Alzheimer's, TBI
Foot Issues	See "Certain infectious and parasitic diseases" in ICD-10-CA *foot only* See "Diseases of the skin and subcutaneous tissue" in ICD-10-CA *foot only* See "Diseases of the musculoskeletal system and connective tissue" in ICD-10-CA *foot only*
Chronic Cardiorespiratory Diseases	See "Diseases of the respiratory system" in ICD-10-CA
Chronic Metabolic Diseases	See "Endocrine, nutritional and metabolic disease" in ICD-10-CA
Cancer	See "Neoplasms" in ICD-10-CA
Pregnancy	See "Pregnancy, childbirth, and the puerperium" in ICD-10-CA
Reproductive Diseases	See "Diseases of the genitourinary system" in ICD-10-CA
Unintentional Injuries	See notes in chart
Other	See notes in chart

Appendix C– Two-page study summary handout

NOWHERE TO GO

Understanding the health of people service restricted from emergency shelters in Hamilton, ON

BACKGROUND

Emergency shelters are meant to provide a temporary place to sleep at night and connect people to services. Service restriction is the practice of limiting or denying the use of an emergency shelter for a set period of time. Service restrictions may affect someone's physical and mental health, and prevent them from accessing important health, social, and housing services.

WHY WE DID THIS RESEARCH

We are a team of doctors, outreach workers, former shelter workers, and people who have been service restricted. We wanted to understand the big picture of who is service restricted, what their health needs are, and how service restriction affects their health. We are sharing our results with community stakeholders, shelter operators and staff, healthcare providers, and the City of Hamilton. We hope our research will influence how service restrictions are implemented, and how people are supported.

WHAT WE DID

We recruited 20 people who have been service restricted in Hamilton. We interviewed them to learn about their service restrictions and their health, and with their permission we reviewed their medical records from local hospitals and the Shelter Health Network.

WHAT WE LEARNED

THEME 1: LOSING YOUR HOME SHOULDN'T MEAN LOSING YOUR HUMANITY

- Some people feel safer and would rather be on the streets than in a shelter because of the violence, stress, and rules in shelters.
- People often feel dehumanized by shelter staff and healthcare workers. They are often stigmatized, labeled, and treated without compassion.
- This was reflected in a high number of people leaving the hospital before their treatment was completed or without being seen by a doctor.

“We're not looked at as people and you're not dealing with life itself, you're now just a number, or just an addiction problem, or a mental health problem, or a disability. And all these different things. And we're not looked at as people anymore so we don't get treated like a person.”

THEME 2: WHERE AM I SUPPOSED TO GO?

- Service restrictions prevent access to health services by displacing people from their usual environments, and push some people to use the Emergency Department more.
- Service restrictions force some people into encampments, where health is made worse by the lack of running water, bathrooms, and ways to maintain personal hygiene.
- This was reflected in a high number of hospital visits for serious infections.

“I just gave up and I just pitched a tent and became a part of that community. Health was horrible. Every single person I came in contact with had some type of infection, sickness. And it was just—yeah, it was just running rife throughout the camps.”

THEME 3: THE SNAKES AND LADDERS GAME OF SERVICE RESTRICTION

- Service restriction rules are confusing and unfair, and sometimes people are restricted without a valid reason.
- Shelters need a standardized and transparent process for service restriction.
- Shelters are a risky environment for people who use drugs; people hide their use to avoid service restriction, making it more dangerous or they end up staying outside.
- This is reflected in a high number of hospital visits for overdoses, along with intoxication, withdrawal, and people seeking detox or treatment.

“Be clear, give warnings, have a protocol for it that they have to follow. A couple of warnings. And the warnings themselves can be appealed. Because I’ve been tricked by that too and kicked out. And they just say that they warned you about something that they didn’t warn you about.”

THEME 4: ALONE TO SURVIVE

- Many people cannot meet their basic needs including getting enough sleep, taking care of personal hygiene, and getting enough to eat.
- People are unsupported in coping with pain, mental and physical illnesses, and homelessness.
- This is reflected in a high number of healthcare visits overall and especially for chronic pain and mental health.

“Self-medicating is really the only way to maintain life as a homeless individual, period. And really that’s all it is. And substance abuse, I don’t even think should be the term used, I think it should just be self-medicating. That’s all it ever is. Nobody abuses substances. They medicate themselves to the point that they feel comfortable again with whatever they have access to.”

THEME 5: CONSTANTLY CRIMINALIZED

- There is a constant police presence in healthcare, and it stops people from accessing healthcare or makes their healthcare experiences harmful.
- Service restriction pushes people into greater conflict with police and the criminal justice system.
- This is reflected in a substantial minority of people being brought to or discharged from hospital in law enforcement custody.

“So I guess when I went to the hospital and they found out my name or whatever, the cops somehow found out my name and ran my name and I had a warrant. So I woke up and I was like handcuffed to the bed. And I had two cops standing in the room.”

THEME 6: HARNESSING THE WISDOM OF COMMUNITY

- There is a strong sense of community and everyone takes care of each other.
- There is a need to improve harm reduction practices and remove current abstinence-based rules in shelters.
- People have many ideas for a better system as a result of experiencing the current limitations and shortfalls that exist.

“I still help people and give the shirt off my own back, and I’m homeless, and have nothing.”

“I’m involved with harm reduction because I believe it saves lives, the people.”

Appendix D – Stakeholder Results Workshop Agenda

Family Medicine

Nowhere to Go - Stakeholder Results Workshop

Wednesday August 2, 2023
 9:00 am to Noon, registration opens at 8:30 am
 David Braley Health Sciences Centre
 100 Main St West
 Hamilton, ON
 Room 1005A
 Masks encouraged!

Getting Here:

[Link to our location on Google maps](#)

We are a 3 minute walk from Frank A. Cooke HSR MacNab Bus Terminal, 1 MacNab St South
 There is bike parking available outside the north side of the building, at the entrance to the building off of Bay St South
 Pay parking at David Braley Health Sciences Centre is \$5 an hour to a maximum of \$20 a day
 Pay parking at City Hall 71 Main St West (surface lot on the south side of the building) is \$3.25 an hour to a maximum of \$15 a day
 Pay parking at the Hamilton Convention Centre 80 Main St West (underground lot) is \$3 an hour to a maximum of \$12 a day

Time	Item
8:30 - 9:00 AM	Registration - Sign in, get your name tag, and enjoy some breakfast!
9:00 - 9:20 AM	Welcome
9:20 - 9:30 AM	Context: service restrictions in Hamilton
9:30 - 10:00 AM	Nowhere to Go: A convergent mixed methods study of the health of people who experience emergency homeless shelter service restriction in Hamilton, ON
10:00 - 10:20 AM	Results: Losing your home shouldn't mean losing your humanity Alone to survive Reflection: How does my humanity connect to the humanity of people who are service restricted?
10:20 - 10:35 AM	Break
10:25 - 10:55 AM	Results: The snakes and ladders of service restriction Constantly criminalized Where am I supposed to go? Discussion: Pair and share thoughts about what you've heard so far

10:55 - 11:45 AM	Results: Harnessing the wisdom of community Brainstorm: Somewhere to Go Collective share back from small group brainstorm
11:45 - Noon	Closing

Appendix E – Stakeholder Results Workshop: Organizations Represented

Note: attendance at workshop does not represent endorsement of the study or results.

City of Hamilton City Councillors (2)

City of Hamilton Housing Services Division

Good Shepherd Centres Hamilton

Hamilton Community Fund

Hamilton Community Legal Clinic

Hamilton Paramedic Service

Hamilton Regional Indian Centre

Indwell

HAMSMaRT

Keeping Six

Department of Family Medicine, McMaster University

Public Health and Preventative Medicine Program, McMaster University

School of Social Work, McMaster University

Mission Services of Hamilton

Shelter Health Network

Social Navigator Program

St Joseph's Healthcare Hamilton

Wesley

YWCA Hamilton